

VITAMIN D STATUS IN SENIOR RESIDENTS OF SAMARKAND REGION

¹Berkinov Abbosjon

²Safarov Firdavs

³Tursunova Sitora

Student of medical course 416 group, Samarkand State Medical University

Scientific adviser: Daminov A.T.

Assistant of the Department of Endocrinology, Samarkand State Medical University

Annotation. Recent studies have significantly expanded the understanding of the spectrum of the biological activity of vitamin D on the state of human health. This vitamin hormone is currently considered as a regulator of the transcriptional activity of genes that control the mineral homeostasis of bone tissue and blood, immune system functions, apoptosis, blood pressure regulation, and other metabolic processes[1,2,5]. The formation of the final, hormonally active form of vitamin D is a rather complex process and depends on the intake of the primary substrate and the metabolism of intermediate forms [7,8,9]. Violation at any level leads to a decrease in the content and activity of vitamin D, which is commonly referred to as "vitamin D deficiency or lack". The results of studies conducted in different countries indicate that about 1 billion people in the world have vitamin D deficiency [3,4,6]. Since most of the biological effects of vitamin D are realized at the genomic level, it is not uncommon for changes in health that occur with its deficiency to not always be directly associated with vitamin D. Currently, a number of diseases or pathological conditions associated with vitamin D deficiency have been identified [16 ,17]. These include osteoporosis and rickets, diseases of the cardiovascular system, certain types of cancer, type 1 diabetes mellitus, damage to the nervous tissue, and some others [10,12,13]. In many countries, vitamin D deficiency is regarded as a "silent epidemic" that has serious medical and medico-social consequences and requires adequate correction [11,14,15]. Since most of the biological effects of vitamin D are realized at the genomic level, it is not uncommon for changes in health that occur with its deficiency to not always be directly associated with vitamin D. Currently, a

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Keywords: Vitamin D, apoptosis, immune system, mineral homeostasis, vitamin hormone.

Target: Study of the level of vitamin D during the period of maximum insolation in elderly and senile people permanently residing in the Samarkand region.

Materials and methods: In the period from 02/20/2023 to 05/20/2023, 70 residents of the Samarkand region (54 women and 16 men) aged 61 to 90 years old were examined for the level of 25(OH) D. Prior to the study, patients did not take vitamin D preparations. The first subgroup consisted of elderly people (Me 66.6 [63.2; 68.4] years). The second subgroup is represented by examined senile patients (Me 81.6 [77.9; 89.2] years). The study was performed by immunochemiluminescent method. Statistical data processing was carried out using the Statistica software package (Stat Soft Inc., USA, version 7.0). The Me index was used in the analysis [25;75].

Research results: All the examined patients were diagnosed with vitamin D deficiency (Me 40.6 [30.7; 52.4] nmol/l), including 68% deficiency. In the first subgroup in women, the level of vitamin D was 45.4 [40.7; 46.7] nmol/l, in men 49.8 [33.9; 55.8] nmol/l. In the second subgroup in men and women 47.1 [26.8; 55.5] nmol/l and 34.6 [25.9; 45.6] nmol/l, respectively. At the same time, in men, unlike women, a negative correlation of the level of 25(OH)D with age was noted ($r=-0.356$ $p<0.001$).

Conclusions: The data obtained demonstrate the presence of vitamin D deficiency in older age groups during the period of maximum insolation in the Samarkand region.

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